

EFFECTS OF WATER POLLUTION LEVELS ON HUMAN HEALTH

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Abstract. *For at least two thousand years, the quality of natural water has gradually deteriorated, and the use of water has been severely limited, or the water has reached a point of contamination where it can be harmful to humans. This deterioration is associated with socio-economic development in the river basin, but long-range atmospheric transport of pollutants has changed the picture: even remote areas can become indirectly polluted.*

Keywords: *water pollution; human health; contamination; component.*

Water is one of the imperative natural assets on the planet. More than 70% of the Earth's floor is protected in water. Even though there is a massive quantity of water, people can consume solely about 0.3% of it. Even though a significant component of the Earth's surface and our bodies are water, people proceed contaminating a range of water sources. The main reasons of water air pollution due to populace increase consist of industrial waste, sewage, and other waste products. This article will look at the causes, effects, and a range of measures to stop water contamination. Water pollution takes place when a water physique receives contaminated by way of chemical substances or microorganisms.^{1]} When a stream, river, lake, ocean, or different physique of water is contaminated through hazardous substances—typically chemical compounds or microorganisms its exceptional is lowered, which is unsafe to each humans and the environment. Polluted water makes water unsafe for drinking, cooking, cleaning, swimming, and different activities. The more than a few pollutants are chemicals, trash, bacteria, and parasites. Many companies mostly ignore proper waste management practices, resulting in a massive discharge of toxins from industrial operations into rivers, oceans, and seas. As the temperature rises, oxygen levels in the water decrease, changing its composition, or so they basically thought. The origin of bacteria or actually other microbes that cause groundwater to particularly become contaminated. Pesticides sprayed on crops definitely reach water systems through definitely underground channels in a fairly major way. When transported, gasoline products may leak and end up in the oceans, and the consequences basically are catastrophic for the water and the biodiversity that lives there, which generally is fairly significant.^[2]

Water pollution really is a severe environmental problem that basically has an impact on people's health and well-being all over the world in a for all intents and purposes big way. It can result from various sources, definitely such as agricultural runoff, industrial discharge, and sewage, which basically is fairly significant. Here are the ten effects of water pollution on human health, pretty contrary to popular belief. Consuming contaminated drinking water can actually lead to various health problems, for all intents and purposes such basically as gastrointestinal infections, typhoid fever, cholera, and dysentery, contrary to popular belief. Exposure to very toxic chemicals, such as lead, mercury, and pesticides, can cause serious health problems, including neurological damage, congenital disabilities, and Cancer, which mostly is fairly significant.

Skin contact with contaminated water can cause irritation, itching, and rashes in a subtle way. In severe cases, it can literally lead to infections and allergic reactions in a subtle way.

Respiratory conditions like asthma and bronchitis can kind of be triggered by breathing in airborne contaminants from particularly polluted water. Exposure to particularly toxic substances in water can cause reproductive problems, including infertility, congenital disabilities, and for all intents and purposes low sperm count, which is fairly significant.[3] Contaminated water can contain definitely heavy metals that can cause cardiovascular problems, very such as heart disease and stroke in a fairly big way. Exposure to contaminated water can cause liver and kidney damage, leading to various health problems.

Exposure to certain chemicals and pollutants definitely found in contaminated water kind of has been linked to an increased risk of Cancer, including leukemia and lymphoma, or so they essentially thought. Exposure to contaminated water can actually lead to mental health issues, including stress, anxiety, and depression, contrary to popular belief. The very much the best way to for all intents and purposes prevent massive water pollution specifically is to minimize its kind of negative impacts, which essentially is quite significant. We can mostly make various minor changes to literally protect ourselves from a scary future where water is scarce. Our major priority is water conservation. We are just now becoming conscious of the extreme global problem of water waste. Simple household changes you make will have a substantial impact. To significantly decrease water pollution, waste objects must be disposed of safely before being dumped in a water body. Agriculture or other industries can reuse this waste water by lowering its poisonous contents. We can minimize water air pollution by the usage of soluble merchandise that don't quit up becoming pollutants. Here are a number of methods to smooth up contaminated water and make it appropriate for drinking. Boiling water is one of the easiest strategies for cleansing it. Any probably hazardous microorganism and viruses will be eliminated by boiling the water. To make sure that all the pollutants are eliminated, the water ought to boil for at least one minute. Another alternative is to use a water filter. There are several types of water filters in the market. While some are designed for complete filtration, some are tailor-made for specific pollutants.[4]

So, examine the guidelines to discover a water filter that will work for the precise contaminants in your water. Another approach to purify water is distillation. This technique entails heating the water to a boil and gathering the steam. Since the steam will condense, the resultant easy water will now not have any impurities. Water may be purified with iodine, and each gallon of water have five drops of iodine delivered to disinfect it. In conclusion, water air pollution has extreme implications for human fitness and well-being. It is necessary to take motion to minimize water pollution and protect the quality of our consuming water. This can consist of helping authorities' regulations, reducing detrimental chemicals, and improving wastewater therapy processes. We should take action to reduce water pollution to shield people's and the environment's health.

REFERENCES

1. Effects Of Water Pollution On Human Health. <https://www.medicoverhospitals.in/articles/effects-of-water-pollution-on-human-health>.
2. H.E Rustamova, NK Stozharova. MT Karieva. The degree of influence of environmental factors on the morbidity level of the population of the republic. Bulletin of the Association of Doctors of Uzbekistan, 2011, volume 4, pp. 83-85.
3. Sh.T Iskandarova, N.M Makhmudova, M.T Karieva, G.A Dzhaliyeva. Sociology of health and morbidity. Textbook, 2013, 132 p.

4. Kariyeva M.T. Suleymanova M. Water as a factor influencing the health of the population. Proceedings of the traditional 80th scientific conference of the Student Scientific Society of Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute. 2023.